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COCKTAIL THERAPY FOR SEVERE GRADE 3 AND GRADE 4 ACNE SCARS

Authors: Dr. Apeksha Merja, Dr. Khushbu R. Modi, Consultant Dermatologist, V.S. Hospital, Ahmedabad

Corresponding author – Dr. Khushbu R. Modi, Consultant Dermatologist, V.S. Hospital, Ahmedabad

Address – A/21, Bandhan Society, Cadila Road, Ghodasar, Maninagar, Ahmedabad.

Phone no. 9998222537.

Abstract

Introduction: The treatment of severe acne scars is challenging due to the variety in morphology of acne scars and the limitations of the available treatment modalities in their ability to improve scars. Tailored treatment plan must be created in which the patient's specific types of scars are treated with the procedures that are most likely to improve those types of scars. This study aims to assess the efficacy of combination therapy using subcision, platelet rich plasma therapy, micro needling and spot 50% TCA CROSS in the management of grade 3 and 4 atrophic scars. **Method:** Twenty-one patients with grade 3 or 4 atrophic acne scars were graded using Goodman and Baron Qualitative grading. Subcision, Platelet Rich Plasma therapy, micro needling and spot 50% TCA CROSS were performed in single sitting for three sessions 1 month apart. Grading of acne scar photographs was done pre-treatment and 1 month after last procedure.

Result: Out of 10 patients with Grade 4 scars, 3 patients improved to Grade 2, 6 patients improved to Grade 3 and 1 patient improved to Grade 1 scars. Out of 11 patients with Grade 3 scars, 1 patient was left with no scars, 3 patients improved to Grade 1 and 7 patients improved to Grade 2.

Conclusion: This combination Subcision, PRP, Micro-needling and TCA CROSS, if they are combined and adequately done in proper manner has shown good results in treating severe Grade 4 and 3 scars.

Keywords

Subcision, PRP, Micro-needling, TCA CROSS

INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is nowadays common in the adolescent age group but inflammatory or excoriated variety of acne will lead to worst complication ever is permanent scarring which is emotionally and psychologically disturbing. Acne which is easier to treat than permanent scars, the actual presence of severe acne scars of grade 3 or 4 linked to low self-esteem¹, anxiety, depression, body image disorders, anger, altered social interactions, decreased academic performance, and unemployment, sometimes suicide.^{2, 3, 4}

Atrophic acne scars with loss or damage of tissue can be classified into icepick, rolling and boxcar scars.⁵ There is no standard treatment option for the treatment of acne scars. Medical management of atrophic scars can be done by using topical retinoids. Surgical management can be done using punch excision, elliptical excision, punch elevation, skin grafting and subcision depending on the type of scar. Procedural management includes microdermabrasion, chemical peels, platelet rich plasma therapy, percutaneous collagen induction by microneedling and dermabrasion. Tissue augmentation can be done using xenografts, autografts and homografts. Various ablative and non-ablative lasers and light energies are also available for treatment of atrophic acne scars.⁵ Out of these multiple treatment options, treatment has to be tailored to patient's needs, tolerance, and goals along with the physician's assessment, skills and expectation. Patient should be counseled that the ultimate goal of any intervention is to

improve the scars and no currently available treatment will attain total cure or perfection. As most of the acne scars appear on the face, it is a major cosmetic concern for a patient and presents a challenge to a dermatologist due to lack of effective treatment modalities. Although many treatment modalities are currently being used, they have shown improvement to a limited extent with possible side effects.⁶

Combination therapy can be defined in multiple ways. Combination therapy can mean utilizing two or more distinct procedures to treat the skin of one patient. Each separate procedure could be performed either on the same day or on different days.⁸ Combination therapy could also mean performing the same procedure multiple times over an extended period of time.⁹

Nowadays severe acne scar treatment modalities are always fascinated by including lasers ablative or non ablative as a thumb rule. Though it is commendable using lasers in acne scars but it adds high amount of cost on therapy. And combination therapy in a single sitting will be very much supported by the patient than having intervals. This will give faster and more compliant response. The side effects of the therapy manifests as a transient erythema, edema pain, post inflammatory hyper pigmentation which are manageable.

The purpose of our study was to evaluate the efficacy of combination therapy using subcision, PRP, dermaroller and 50% spot TCA CROSS for the management of atrophic severe acne scars Grade 3 and 4.

METHOD

Twenty one patients with atrophic acne scar grade 3 or 4 presenting to the outpatient department of dermatology, venereology, leprosy in a tertiary care centre, were enrolled for the study. It was a prospective study over the period from February 2019 to December 2019.

The inclusion criteria included age group 18–35 years and cases with atrophic acne scars (Grade 3 and 4) according to Goodman and Baron's classification system.¹³

The exclusion criteria included active acne, history of keloid, bleeding disorder, lignocaine hypersensitivity, pregnancy or lactation, immunocompromised status, and unrealistically high expectations. A proper informed consent was taken.

The atrophic acne scars were graded by a single non-treating physician using Goodman and Baron Qualitative scar grading system¹³

Eutectic mixture of lignocaine 2% and prilocaine 2% cream was applied under occlusion for 1 hour to the affected areas which was removed using gauze. At the start of treatment, subcision was performed only once using a 24G needle, Twenty milliliters of autologous whole blood was collected from the median cubital vein in vacutainer tube containing an anticoagulant acid citrate dextrose-A. PRP was obtained manually by a two-step procedure using a centrifuge machine (Remi R4-C) First spin was performed at 1000 RPM for 12 min at room temperature. It was done to separate plasma with platelets and white blood cells from red blood cells (RBCs). RBCs being heavy settled down at the bottom. The plasma was gently aspirated from each tube and was transferred to a plain vacutainer bulb without anticoagulant. Second spin was performed at room temperature at the rate of 2000 RPM for 5 min, thus obtaining a two-part plasma. Upper two third, being poor in platelets, was platelet-poor plasma (PPP) and lower one third, being rich in platelets, was PRP. PRP was then injected intradermally through a 30G needle (insulin syringe) deep to each scar on both the cheeks. The amount injected was sufficient to elevate the scar, and the end point was taken as blanching and elevation of the scar.

The site was gently massaged and compressed for a few seconds to control the bleeding. Microneedling with dermaroller containing 192 needles of needle size 1.5 mm. Treatment was performed by rolling the dermaroller in vertical, horizontal and diagonal directions in the affected area until appearance of uniform fine pinpoint bleeding. Then the area was wiped with saline soaked gauze. Then 50% spot TCA CROSS peel was done in deep scars involving

specifically ice pick scar. Appearance of speckled white frosting was the end point of treatment. Topical antibiotic cream (fusidic acid 2% cream) was applied to the treated area. The patients were given topical sunscreen. Fluticasone propionate cream 0.05% twice daily for 5 days if needed was given. The patients were reviewed on the 3rd day and on the 7th day for any side effects. The same procedure protocol was repeated monthly for 3 months. Patients were evaluated for grading of acne scars according to Goodman Baron classification 1 month after the last procedure. Patient was asked to grade their subjective response to treatment as poor, good, very good or excellent with 0-24%, 25-49%, 50-74% and 75-100% improvement, respectively, in their acne scars.

RESULTS

[FIGURE 1 patient having grade 4 scars improved to grade 2 scars]

[FIGURE 2 patient having grade 4 scars improved to grade 1 scars]

[FIGURE 3 patient having grade 3 scars improved to grade 1 scars]

[FIGURE 4 patient having grade 3 scars improved to grade 1 scars]

Twenty one patients included in study (7 male, 14 female) from 18-35 years of age group. Out of 10 patients with Grade 4 scars, 3 patients improved to Grade 2, 6 patients improved to Grade 3 and 1 patient improved to Grade 1 scars. Out of 11 patients with Grade 3 scars, 1 patient was left with no scars, 3 patients improved to Grade 1 and 7 patients improved to Grade 2. [Figure 1-4]. Hence all patients (100%) had improvement in their scars by improvement in some grade with no failure rate. In Grade 4 scars group, 4 patients graded their response to treatment as very good (50-74% improvement) and 6 patients had good improvement (25-49% improvement). In patients with Grade 3 scars, 8 patients graded their response to treatment as excellent (75-100% improvement) and 6 patients reported the response as very good (50-74% improvement).

On comparing individual scar results, rolling scars showed excellent improvement than boxcars and ice pick scars. All patients tolerated the procedure well. Side effects were mild and transient. Post-dermaroller transient erythema and oedema lasted for 1-4 days. Post spot 50% TCA CROSS exfoliation of skin was present from 2 to 7 days and post inflammatory erythema lasted 10 to 15 days. The PIH subsided after 2 months of topical treatment. All patients were having post procedure mild pain which lasted for 2 to 3 days and which was manageable with oral analgesics.

DISCUSSION

The rationale for combining these minimally invasive procedures was their additive action on various types of acne scars by different mechanism.

Subcision, also called as subcutaneous incisionless surgery, Subcision releases the scars from the underlying adhesions which should be the first step for any treatment for acne scars. The depression is lifted by the releasing action of the procedure, as well as from connective tissue that forms during the course of normal wound healing.¹⁰ Subcision is a safe, simple technique

that provides significant long-term improvement in the “rolling scars” of selected patients. It can be safely and easily combined with other treatments for acne scars.

The therapeutic use of autologous PRP is a relatively new biotechnology in the stimulation and acceleration of soft-tissue healing. Its procedural safety is well established due to its autologous nature. PRP provides various growth factors which aid in quick wound healing. PRP when injected into the damaged area causes mild inflammation. The basis of this process is local and continuous delivery of a wide range of growth factors such as platelet-derived growth factor, transforming growth factor beta, platelet-derived epidermal growth factor, platelet-derived angiogenesis factor, insulin-like growth factor 1, and platelet factor 4 and proteins.¹¹ All of these stimulate the physiological wound healing and reparative tissue processes. It is used as an adjuvant therapy for acne scars.

These microinjuries lead to minimal superficial bleeding and set up a wound healing cascade with release of various growth factors such as platelet derived growth factor (PGF), transforming growth factor alpha and beta (TGF- α and TGF- β), connective tissue activating protein, connective tissue growth factor, and fibroblast growth factor (FGF).¹² The needles also breakdown the old hardened scar strands and allow it to revascularize. Neovascularization and neocollagenesis is initiated by migration and proliferation of fibroblasts and laying down of intercellular matrix. Fifty percent spot TCA CROSS acts by focusing on the dermal thickening, collagen production and improvement in skin texture. Hence by combining these cost effective modalities one can release the scars, enhance collagen induction and resurface the skin.

COCLUSION

Acne scar is routinely seen as a cosmetic concern both by patients and doctors point of view, but it is a permanent complication of acne which brings so many emotional and psychological disturbances. Mild to moderate type of acne scars can be camouflaged but severe acne scars cannot be, and always needs some type of treatment. In this study combination of minimally invasive procedures in single sitting is affordable for patients as opposed to high cost of laser procedures. Side effects associated with this cocktail approach are also minimal and manageable.

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